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Research Article

**MEDICO-LEGAL CASES: NATURE, FREQUENCY AND
PERCENTAGE AT LUHMS HYDERABAD, PAKISTAN.**Muhammad Qasim¹, Jamshed ul Qadir², Abdul Samad³, Muhammad Akber Kazi⁴

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Abstract:

Medico-legal cases are among the daily practice all around the globe to claim one's rights and to punish the culprit. The nature of medicolegal cases varies from area to area and social and cultural values of every region. The current research work conducted in the medicolegal section of the Liaquat University Hospital from January 2015 to 31 December 2015. Patients of all age groups of both genders were included registered as medico-legal while non-medicolegal cases were excluded. Data generated was analyzed on SPSS Version 22. Total 3636 patients were seen in one year duration top most proportion was of assault 2758(75.85%), followed by RTA 489(13.45%), fire arm 191(5.25%), alcohol intoxication 92(2.53%), poisoning 34(0.94%) and train accidents 22(0.61%), others (0.61%) rape 19(0.52%), 05(0.13%), police torture 3(0.08%). Maximum cases presented in June 388(%), followed by 372(%) in April, 323(%) in July, 322(%) in August, 313(%) in September, 383(%) in May, 271(%) in Feb, 270(%) in March, 251(%) in December, 250(%) in November, 248(%) in January and 245(%) in October.

Conclusion:

Assault was found to be the most common medico-legal presentations followed by road traffic accidents in the Hyderabad region of Sindh province of Pakistan.

Key Words: *Medico-legal, Assaults, RTA, alcohol Intoxication*

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INTRODUCTION:

Medicolegal cases (MLCs) are defined as injuries requiring investigations to fix the responsibility regarding the cause of injury through law-enforcing agencies [1]. MLCs may be injuries suggesting offenses or accidental injuries, all unnatural deaths, suspected sexual assault, suspected criminal abortion, unconsciousness with clear cause, suspected poisoning or intoxication, cases referred from court, cases that are brought dead with suspected offense, suspected self-inflicted injuries or suicidal attempt and any other case that some legal importance. Majority of doctors usually avoid dealing with MLCs due to their apprehension regarding the lengthy legal procedure and dispute and political pressures all disturbing their routine practice and social life. Medico-legal cases need to be dealt properly with clear institutional guidelines and almost all hospitals as well as teaching institutions possess 'institutional medico-legal manual' but even if no such manual is available MLCs do not pose any problem if dealt with proper caution, care and attention such as proper documentation, information, thorough examination-necessary investigations and if required the referral[2]. Registered medical practitioner is responsible to judge every MLC properly and inform the law enforcement authorities which saves him from unnecessary allegations in future [3]. Medico-legal cases usually observed in common practice in the sub-continent are usually lodged to put a pressure on the opposite party in a clash, to take revenge or to obtain an extra favor from the judiciary. MLC cases vary in their nature, frequency and percentage from region to region as well as they do have some seasonal variations. There was no regional

data available on literature search in this perspective from the Hyderabad, Pakistan so this study was arranged to discover the pattern of MLCs in this particular region.

METHODOLOGY:

The medicolegal section of the Liaquat University Hospital was selected for the current research work as center for data collection as it is the main hospital of the region at a tertiary care level. Duration of the study was from 01/01/2015 to 31/12/2015. Consecutive sampling type of non-probability sampling was used to select the patients of both genders from age groups with medico-legal cases as the only inclusion criteria while non-medico-legal cases were set as exclusion criteria. SPSS Version 22 was used to analyze the data generated.

RESULTS:

Total number of MLCs was 3636 in one year most patients were from assaults group 75.85%(2758), RTA was the 2nd most common category 13.45%(489), while fire arm stood at 3rd position 5.25%(191) followed by alcohol intoxication 2.53%(92), poisoning 0.94%(34), train accidents 0.61%(22), others 0.61%(22) rape 0.52%(19), 05(0.13%)(05), police torture 0.08%(03). Highest number of cases were seen the month of June 10.69%(388), April was second highest 10.23%(372), July 8.88% (323), in August it was 8.83%(322), in September 8.61%(313), in May 7.78%(383), in Feb 7.48%(271), it was 7.69%(270) in March, it was 6.90%(251) in December, 6.88%(250) in November, 6.82%(248) in January and 6.82%(245) in October.

Table#01. Monthly distribution of the study population with nature, frequency and percentage

Months	Assaults	RTA	Fire Arm	Alcohol Intoxication	Poisoning	Train Accident	Rape	Police Torture	Sodomy	Others	Total
January	174	31	36	03	00	00	01	00	01	02	248(6.82%)
February	174	36	18	07	09	20	02	00	00	04	271(7.48%)
March	192	39	26	08	00	00	01	00	00	04	270(7.42%)
April	287	50	11	19	03	00	01	00	01	00	372(10.23%)
May	316	40	08	12	02	01	00	02	00	02	283(7.78%)
June	320	42	12	10	01	00	01	00	01	01	388(10.67%)
July	252	39	18	05	01	01	03	01	01	02	323(8.88%)
August	258	40	14	07	00	00	02	00	00	01	322(8.86%)
September	242	44	17	03	02	00	03	00	00	02	313(8.61%)
October	189	34	14	02	03	00	01	00	00	02	245(6.84%)
November	193	33	05	03	11	00	03	00	01	01	250(6.88%)
December	161	61	12	13	02	00	01	00	00	01	251(6.90%)
Total (Disease)	2758 (75.9%)	489 (13.5%)	191 (5.3%)	92 (2.53%)	34 (0.94%)	22 (0.61%)	19 (0.5%)	03 (0.08%)	05 (0.14%)	22 (0.6%)	3636(100%)

DISCUSSION:

Multiple international studies are available on the current topic enhancing its importance. Jitendra T et al (2017) reported in his study results that the majority of cases (81.84%) presented as MLCs were accidental cases, 9.73% were suicidal cases while 8.42% were homicidal cases, 9.21% poisoning cases, assault cases were reported as 8.02% and dead bodies received were 3.09%, these findings were inconsistent with findings which showed highest number of cases of assault 75.9% followed by 13.5% of RTA. He also reported maximum number of cases presenting in March that was 11.11% followed by 9.28% of the September in his monthly distribution of MLCs that was inconsistent to our results with maximum 10.67% cases seen in June and 10.23% in April as second highest cases reporting month [4]. Our results were also inconsistent with the results of Siddappa SC et al (2015) who found accidental cases on top with 69.03% and suicidal cases at 2nd number with 20.24% and homicidal on number three with 10.72% possibly due to cultural differences and life style differences between the two areas [5]. Yadav A et al (2013) reported in his study results assault cases on top (39.6%) followed by accidental cases (38.1%) these findings were inconsistent to our study results [6]. Another inconsistent result was seen from the study results of Malik Y et al (2013) who declared poisoning as the observed maximum number of cases reported [7]. Hussain SN et al (2013) found burn cases on top in his research work that was also an inconsistent finding as compared to our study results

[8]. MLCs are different depending on the regional distribution in terms of their nature, frequency and percentage. A Pakistani study from Rawal Pindi by Malik R et al (2017) revealed August as the month with maximum number 314 (10.41%) of MLCs followed by November and January 298 (9.88%) and 288 (9.55%) respectively. His study showed 3015 patients of MLCs to visit the tertiary care hospital and most of them (38%) were of RTA and 32% were physical assault while 19% were reported to be sharp weapon injury [9]. This study was also inconsistent to the present study in monthly distribution and frequency and percentage along with the nature of the MLCs even in the same country. The medico legal cases are responsible for mortalities and morbidities throughout the globe that still needs effective measures to control as this expected mortality is going to cross the mortality due to communicable diseases by 2020 [10]. Hopefully with the time countries will recognize MLCs among their major public health concerns that will be the turning point for the human society. We recommend public awareness programs in the public communities as an initial move.

CONCLUSION:

Assault was found to be the most common medico-legal presentations followed by road traffic accidents in the Hyderabad region of Sindh province of Pakistan.

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